
2. Two Kinds of Creator: Distinguishing the *Kalam* and Thomistic Cosmological Arguments

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ABSTRACT: This article contrasts two versions of the cosmological argument: the *kalam* version and Thomas Aquinas' version. Highlighting the distinctions between them is essential to avoid confusions while presenting and criticizing each of the arguments. Christian apologists might be tempted to claim that Thomas defended the origin of the universe, while critics may try to criticize Thomas' argument thinking that's what the argument is about. The *kalam* cosmological argument, developed by Arabic theologians such as Al-Kindi and Al-Ghazali, is about the origin of the universe, but that is not the case with the Thomistic version, which is highly inspired by Aristotelian thought and Arabic philosophers from the Middle Ages. Since there are profound metaphysical distinctions between the two, it's important to explain each of the arguments and emphasize its differences with the other. At the end of the article is a discussion on which of these arguments might be better for contemporary apologetics.

TRADITIONALLY, according to William Lane Craig, there are two types of creation in Christian theology: *creatio originans* and *creatio continuans*. The first refers to the question of God as the Creator of the universe at a specific point at which the universe began to exist; the latter is about the preservation

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of reality in each instant of its existence.² While such a distinction is important, some people seem unaware of it when discussing cosmological arguments. In traditional natural theology, the cosmological argument has been defended in a variety of different versions: from the unmoved mover argument by Aristotle, to the Arabic form by medieval philosophers such as Avicenna, Averroes and Al-Ghazali, to more modern presentations. Its basic premises now feature in contemporary discussions with prominent philosophers like William Lane Craig, Robert Koons, Joshua Rasmussen and Alexander Pruss.

Recently, however, those versions of the cosmological argument have encountered critics that don't seem to be aware of its differences. For example, Richard Dawkins has publicly tried to refute Thomas Aquinas' first three ways to prove God's existence with a critique that, at best, would apply to Al-Ghazali's/Craig's version. In talking about Thomas' argument, Dawkins discusses how the Big Bang cosmological singularity or other unknown physical concept would be a "more parsimonious" alternative than God.³ To call the first cause "God" is, according to Dawkins, "at best unhelpful and at worst perniciously misleading."⁴

Given such confusion, it would seem useful to present the deep metaphysical distinction between those two versions of the cosmological argument. More precisely, that distinction will be made through a presentation of both arguments: the *kalam* cosmological argument and the Thomistic cosmological argument. In doing so, the differences will be made clear.

² William Lane Craig, "What Place, Then, for a Creator?": Hawking on God and Creation," *The British Journal for the Philosophy of Science* 41, no. 4 (1990): 475–76.

³ Richard Dawkins, *The God Delusion* (New York: Houghton-Mifflin, 2006), 78.

The kalam cosmological argument

This version of the cosmological argument was developed by Al-Kindi (801-873 AD) and, later, by Al-Ghazali (1058-1111 AD). They both were from the *kalam* school of Islamic theology in the Middle Ages (476-1453 AD) and defended a view of God as the creator, in time, of the universe. Although they both defended the same version of the cosmological argument, they differ in their approach. Key to this argument is the notion that the world had an absolute beginning in time. Al-Kindi and Al-Ghazali differ on how they could prove such a point.

Al-Kindi argued that for each moment of time there is another moment preceding it. However, it is not possible to have an infinite regress of such moments, for, “if it were possible, and after every segment of time there was a segment, infinitely, then we would never reach a given time”.⁵ This is basically a form of the argument against an infinite regress of days: if there were an infinite amount of days prior to today, then today would never arrive. Since it arrived (we’re here), therefore the past is not infinite.

Al-Ghazali argued from a similar perspective, but using the impossibility of an infinite series of temporal phenomena. For example, according to the cosmology of his time, Ghazali believed that the Sun, Saturn and Jupiter revolved around the Earth. The Sun thus revolves once per year, while Saturn revolves thirty and Jupiter twelve. Now, if the past were eternal, that would mean that even Saturn doing 1/30 of revolutions of the Sun per year and Jupiter doing 1/12, would imply that all of them made infinite revolutions around the Earth.⁶

⁴ Dawkins, 78.

⁵ Al-Kindi, *On First Philosophy*, in Alfred L. Ivry, *Al-Kindi’s “First Philosophy” and Cognate Texts: Translation and Commentary* (Ph.D. dissertation, University of Oxford, 1970), 121.

⁶ Al-Ghazali. *Tahafut al-falasifah: Incoherence of the Philosophers*, (Pakistan Philosophical Congress, Club Road: Lahore: 1963), 20.

That already shows, according to Ghazali, that the past cannot be infinite, but he has more to say: if the number of revolutions were infinite, then it would not be even nor odd, or it would be both, which is impossible.⁷

Ghazali's argument is presented simply as follows: every occurrent has a cause; the world is an occurrent; necessarily, therefore, the world has a cause.⁸ Craig has simplified the argument as follows:

1. Everything that begins to exist has a cause.
2. The universe began to exist.
3. Therefore, the universe had a cause.

In this version, Craig adapts Ghazali's argument against an infinite regress of temporal phenomena to modern astronomy and adds the scientific confirmation of modern cosmology to show that the universe had a beginning.⁹

The key here is to understand that the *kalam* cosmological argument appeals strongly to the finitude of the past to argue that God is the Creator. In this regard, the argument doesn't stop on the demonstration of the origin of the universe but also presents a conceptual analysis of its cause. Given that the universe comprises all of space, time and matter, this cause must be timeless, spaceless and immaterial. It must also be extremely powerful, since it created the universe from nothing. Moreover, it must be personal, since it had to freely decide "when" to create the universe. Since there is no distinction between a moment or another in an eternal temporal past, nor does a timeless permanent state present any special property to begin a temporal

⁷ Al-Ghazali, *Al-Ghazali's Moderation in Belief*. (Chicago, IL, USA: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 38.

⁸ Al-Ghazali, 56.

⁹ See William Lane Craig. *The kalām cosmological argument*. 2^a Ed., (Eugene, OR: Wipf and Stock Publishers, 2000); William Lane Craig & James Sinclair, "The kalam cosmological argument", In: J. P. Moreland & William Lane Craig (Org.), *The Blackwell Companion to natural theology*. (West Sussex: Wiley-Blackwell, 2012).

effect, the cause must freely choose to create the universe. Such a concept is essentially what everybody means by God.

The Thomistic cosmological argument

Thomas Aquinas' cosmological argument is presented in his first "three ways" (of his famous Five Ways) to prove God's existence. The first way is based on Aristotle's Unmoved Mover argument, the second is based on Avicenna's cosmological argument and the third one is a version of Averroes argument. Key concepts are necessary to understand all three arguments:

First, the distinction between *act* and *potency*. To explain this distinction, it is useful to appeal to a practical example: the seed of an apple tree has the *potency* to become an apple tree. When it arrives at such a state it is an apple tree in *act*. Now, this movement from seed to apple requires a *mover*. Aristotle argued that the universe contains spheres that moved from eternity past. Therefore, they require an eternal mover. Since an infinite regress of movers is impossible, therefore this is an Unmoved Mover.¹⁰ Thomas used this argument as the First Way. He says that, since everything that moves is moved by another, there cannot be an infinite regress of movers and, therefore, it is "necessary to arrive at a first mover, not moved by any other, and this, everyone understands: it is God."¹¹

Second, the difference between *essence* and *existence*. While the essence of a thing is its own nature, it contains the potency of existence.¹² Etienne Gilson explains that Al-Farabi, who made the distinction prior to Avicenna, "was inspired by Aristotle's observation that the notion of what a thing is does not include the fact that the thing is".¹³ To be actualized in the world, a thing requires an efficient cause. For Avicenna, the order of

¹⁰ See Aristotle, *Metafísica* Λ, 6, 1071b - 7, 1072b.

¹¹ Thomas Aquinas, *Summa Theologica*, I, q. 2, a. 3. ad. 1.

¹² William Lane Craig, *The cosmological argument from Plato to Leibniz*. (Nova Iorque: The MacMillan Press, 1980), 77.

¹³ Etienne Gilson, *A filosofia na Idade Média*. 2ª. Ed. (São Paulo: Martins Fontes, 2007), 428.

efficient causes cannot be infinite, even in an eternal cosmos. What that means is that, for Avicenna (and latter for Thomas), the order of efficient causes is not necessarily one “before” the other, but something that makes another exist, even if it is eternal. In other words, something *depends* on another to exist. The universe can exist eternally – from past eternity to endless future – but it requires a cause to keep existing. Therefore, the whole universe requires a cause that contains existence as part of its own essence; you cannot have an infinite regress of contingent causes.

Contrary to things that require a cause – which are contingent – this First Cause is necessary¹⁴, for it cannot fail to exist, since existence is in its nature.¹⁵ God, explains Anthony Kenny, “created by necessity: he is absolute goodness, and goodness, by force of its nature, radiates outwards. But if God is necessarily a creator, then creation must be eternal just as God is eternal.”¹⁶ Thomas bases his Second Way in this argument. He writes: “nor is it possible, among efficient causes, to continue to infinity, because among all ordered efficient causes, the first is the cause of the intermediate ones and the intermediate ones are the cause of the last, whether they are numerous or only one.” And he concludes: “If there were no first among efficient causes, there would be no last or intermediate....Therefore, it is necessary to affirm a first efficient cause, which everyone calls God.”¹⁷

¹⁴ Here, the concept of “contingent” and “necessary” is different from the one use in contemporary modal logic. Avicenna and other medieval philosophers and theologians are not interested in possible worlds, but rather on the dependence or independence of things from another beings.

¹⁵ Avicenne. *Métaphysique du shifa*, Vol. II, Books VI-X, (Librairie Philosophique J. Vrin, 1985), 71.

¹⁶ Anthony Kenny, *Uma nova história da filosofia: filosofia medieval*, Vol. 2, 2ª Ed., (São Paulo: Edições Loyola, 2012), 325.

¹⁷ Aquinas, *Su. Th.* I, q. 2, a. 3. ad. 1.

Third is Averroes' argument, which is based on the distinction between "truly possible" beings and "possible-necessary" beings.¹⁸ Craig explains that the truly possible is anything caused and perishable; the necessary-possible, by contrast, is anything that maintains the caused nature of perishable being, but is not susceptible to generation or corruption.¹⁹ Averroes argued: "Possible existents must, of necessity, have causes that precede them, and if these causes are again possible, it follows that they have other causes, there being an infinite regress; but if there is an infinite regress, then there is no cause at all, and the possible will exist without a cause, which is impossible."²⁰ If such an infinite regress is impossible, then what is the first cause: truly possible or necessary-possible? Averroes argued that this first cause must be simply necessary, which does not have a cause.²¹ Based on that, Thomas says in his presentation of the Third Way:

...we observe that there are things in the world that can be and not be, such as those subject to generation and corruption. Now, everything that is possible to be has a cause, because insofar as it refers in itself to two terms, that is, to being and non-being, it requires, if being is appropriate to it, that this occurs from a cause. But, since one cannot proceed indefinitely in causes [...] one must admit something that is necessarily being.

However, every necessary being has the cause of its necessity coming either from another or from itself, insofar as it is necessary in itself. Now, one cannot proceed indefinitely in the series of necessary beings that have the cause of their necessity coming from another. Therefore, one must admit a

¹⁸ Averroes. *Tahafut al tahafut: The Incoherence of the Incoherence*, Vol. I e II, (Cambridge: EJW Gibb Memorial Trust, 1987), 164.

¹⁹ William Lane Craig, *The Cosmological Argument from Plato to Leibniz*, 106.

²⁰ Averroes, 165.

²¹ Averroes, 165.

being that is the first necessary and that is necessary in itself. This being is God, insofar as God is the first cause, as was demonstrated above. Therefore, God is eternal, since everything necessary in itself is eternal.²²

Notice that Thomas' is not requiring a beginning in time of the world. Rather, since Aristotle, Avicenna and Averroes believed in the eternity of the world, and Thomas' argument works in an eternal universe. To illustrate that, imagine a lighter that exists from eternity past. The *kalam* argument proponent would argue that it is necessary that the fire begin at some point in the lighter. On the other hand, a Thomistic view (and Aristotelian or Arabic philosophy view) would say that the fire is burning from eternity past. The cause of the fire is, in both cases, the lighter, but one makes the fire *begin* to exist, while the other simply makes the fire *permanently* exist.

Closing remarks

Both versions of the cosmological argument differ significantly in their metaphysical foundations and implications. While the *kalam* argument hinges on the impossibility of an eternal universe (with an infinite series of past events), the Thomistic version is more metaphysical in its appeal to concepts such as act and potency, essence and existence, and contingency and necessity. Thomas' argument can be divided into three different cosmological arguments influenced by Aristotle, Avicenna and Averroes. It is, however, the compatibility of Thomas' argument with an infinite past that differentiates it from the *kalam* version. Al-Kindi, Al-Ghazali and modern proponents of the *kalam* cosmological argument need the past to be finite to argue for God as the first cause, while Thomas Aquinas' first three ways works with an eternal universe and argue for God as a Cause that is First – Uncaused, Unmoved and Necessary.

It is important to say that even though the authors disagree about the role of God as the Creator in a metaphysical sense, the arguments do not contradict each other. The Thomistic argu-

²² Thomas Aquinas, *Summa contra Gentiles.*, I, c. XV, 124.

ment is compatible with an eternal universe but does not necessitate one. One might hold that God created the universe at some point in the finite past, but also that He sustains it's being as an efficient cause. This would warrant philosophically the Christian idea presented at the beginning of this article – that of *creatio originans* and *creatio continuans*.

Although both versions seem to have their strengths, these days it would be preferable to argue using the *kalam* rather than the Thomistic argument. The Thomistic version of the cosmological argument depends too much on Aristotelian metaphysics, which might be difficult to explain; and even bypassing that obstacle the argument might sound outdated, since some of Aristotle's thought is based on ancient cosmology (like the idea that the celestial spheres revolve eternally). The *kalam* argument is more in line with contemporary cosmology and mathematics, thanks largely to the work of William Lane Craig. Besides that, it is easier to explain that since everything that begins has a cause and the universe had a beginning, it also requires a cause. Thomas' argument is good for philosophical discussions in academia, but not a good argument for popular apologetics.